

LEXICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPUTER TERMS IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

The study of Uzbek and Karakalpak linguistic words is examined in this scientific article, which looks at terminological writings on linguistic terminology produced between 1920 and the present, including research articles, scientific collections, monographs, and other publications.

Keywords: terminology, linguistic phenomenon, terminology, jargon, slang, internet, computer, technology, language, professional.

Numerous scientific investigations on the analysis of linguistic words have been carried out in Uzbekistan up to this point. Scholars Abdurauf Fitrat (1886–1938) and Mashrik Yunusov (Elbek) (1898–1939) offered ideas about the scientific validation of linguistic words [1,336]. Fitrat, who also penned "Sarf" and "Nahv," advanced the notion that "we need to work a little harder and help each other to clarify all the rules of our language and put their terms on the field." Sarf examines the morphology and phonetics of the Uzbek language, whereas Nahv examines the meanings of terms pertaining to speech, parts of speech, ordered sections, speech kinds, and introduction words. He goes into detail on the meaning and history of the term "cut," which is one of the main parts of speech, in a unique way: [1:76] “..1. Birds sing in the morning in the garden. 2. We say that Chulpon recently wrote a good poem, and what we want to explain is to stop the game. It's a matter of words. At the end of the speech, the word was cut off. That is why he wrote at the end of the above two sentences, we call the words "sayra" "cut words of the sentence" or simply "cut" [1.333]. There are also punctuation marks, full stops (.), One pause (;), a semicolon (,), a question mark (?), A consonant (!), A colon (:), quotation marks (“”). , terms such as bows (()), four-pointed bows ([]), large bows ({}), lines (-), dots (...) are also explained.

Elbek's research also takes into account the study of language words. He advanced certain scientific and theoretical concepts in the fields of phonetics and morphemes during the process of elucidating the theoretical and practical aspects of these words in linguistics. He uses the term "vowel" in phonetics to describe the speech and writing sounds: Additionally, there are phrases pertaining to vowels, vowels, and the classification of vowels, such as thick upper vowels (o), thin upper vowels (a), and long

vowels (vowels); ost bottoms, thick ost bottles (e), thin ost bottles (i). Regarding consonants, he referred to them as continuous and long vowels. [2:33]

Concurrently, he clarified the meaning of words and adjectives. Uzbek language, and A. Khodzhiyev examined the standards used in word selection as well as the condition of Uzbek linguistic terminology. Throughout his research of linguistic terminology, I.R. Ermatov selected terms from textbooks, councils, and textbooks from the era of independence that were produced throughout this process. Though with certain limitations, he claims that Uzbek linguistic terminology started to take shape in the 1920s. Since the original textbooks were written within the confines of grammar, the majority of these words are grammatical. This study is a first effort to examine the mutual reliance and exchange of linguistic terminology between Uzbek Karakalpak and Russian.

CONCLUSION

This dissertation examines, for the first time, how Russian linguistic words influenced the creation and evolution of Uzbek linguistic vocabulary. A comparative analysis of language words was carried out in the work of AN Rajabov two years later. The study of linguistic terms in the Uzbek and Russian languages is examined in this dissertation through the examination and analysis of materials from scientific research studies, textbooks, manuals, terminological dictionaries, monographs, collections of Uzbek and Russian linguistic terminology, and other publications published between 1970 and 1992. given In the course of AN Rajabov's research, words were chosen in compliance with State law. A comparative and comparative lexicographic examination of linguistic words was also carried out by DI Khodjaeva using the materials of the explanatory dictionaries of the English, Russian, and Uzbek languages. The study's analysis of linguistic terms is characterized by the following terminological requirements: precision, logical coherence, structure, adherence to literary language norms, popularity, and interlinguistic lexical-semantic characteristics of linguistic terms, as well as the degree of codification in explanatory dictionaries.

The research of linguistic terms as a separate functional layer was conducted using Chinese linguistic terminology as an example. It also examined the stages and methods of these terms' production as well as the scientific validation of structural and lexical-semantic properties. Within it, the researcher formulated guidelines regarding the management of Chinese language terminology, mitigating issues with their translation into Uzbek, steering clear of literal and indirect translations, and providing equivalent terms in Karakalpak through this substitute.

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